

Palaeolandscape reconstruction of a shallow coastal embayment in Kattegat, Denmark—influence of sea-level changes during the latest Pleistocene and Holocene

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Shallow coastal embayments are typical features of former glacial landscapes in parts of Scandinavia and North America. An increasing concern over the impact of accelerating sea-level rise, calls for a better understanding of how coasts respond to sea-level changes. Studying the response of coastal environments, such as submerged embayments, to sea-level changes in the past, can provide important insights into the response of present-day coastlines to future sea-level rise. Kalø Bay is an embayment situated in south-western Kattegat, north of the Aarhus Bay, Denmark. This shallow embayment was influenced by sea-level changes governed by global sea-level rise and glacio-isostatic rebound from the Scandinavian Ice Sheet during the latest Pleistocene and Holocene. In this study, we analyse the palaeolandscape in the bay to identify the depositional succession preserved in the bay and understand the dominant geological processes occurring after the last glaciation in response to sea-level changes. Four major depositional units reflect the variable environment in the bay as it changed from a glacial to proglacial setting through coastal and lagoonal infill stages, and gradually developed into a shallow marine environment as the area was inundated approximately 9–6 cal. ka BP. During a relative sea-level fall in the Mid- and Late Holocene, the deposits in the bay reversed to more coastal facies. Our study highlights the sensitivity of coastal embayments and their dynamic response to sea-level changes. Our results show how the bay changed from a wave-dominated setting in the Early Holocene to a current-dominated setting in the Late Holocene, and how the former glacial landscape and coastal deposits were affected differently by the sea-level rise and associated erosion and redeposition. These results are important for understanding the impacts of future accelerating sea-level rise.

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Shallow embayments, such as coastal bays, estuaries and lagoons, represent depositional environments that are particularly sensitive to sea-level changes due to their shallow waters and coastal zones with average heights close to mean sea-level (e.g. Dalrymple *et al.* 1992; Reading 1996; Barboza *et al.* 2021; Blázquez *et al.* 2024). Sediment from such areas typically shows evidence of marine, coastal and fluvial processes with deposits characterized by tidal influence, wave activity and riverine inputs (e.g. Boyd *et al.* 1992; Dalrymple *et al.* 1992; Hein *et al.* 2012; Sander *et al.* 2015; Ranasinghe *et al.* 2021). Depending on base levels, sediment supply and accommodation space, the various sedimentary facies in shallow embayments have different preservation potentials, generally with limited preservation due to the shallow waters (e.g. Davis & Clifton 1987). Shallow embayments, however, are influenced by even minor sea-level changes and hence also have the potential of recording such in the geological succession (e.g. Sander *et al.* 2016; Andresen *et al.* 2021; Bennike *et al.* 2022). Therefore, they represent

an important archive of complex sea-level history and geological development.

In Denmark, the relative sea-level changes after the Last Glacial Maximum (LGM; Marine Isotope Stage (MIS) 2) are controlled by the interplay of glacio-isostatic adjustments from the Scandinavian Ice Sheet (e.g. Mertz 1924; Lambeck *et al.* 1998; Vink *et al.* 2007; Hughes *et al.* 2016) and the rise in global eustatic sea-level from approximately 130 m below present-day mean sea-level (Lambeck *et al.* 2014). Our study area is situated in the south-western part of Kattegat close to the city of Aarhus (Fig. 1). The dynamics of the sea-level changes in the Kattegat region have been addressed in several studies (e.g. Bennike *et al.* 2004, 2012; Bennike & Jensen 2011; Bendixen *et al.* 2013, 2015; Sander *et al.* 2016; Astrup 2018; Vestøl *et al.* 2019; Rasmussen *et al.* 2020; Riis *et al.* 2024). According to a recent relative shore-level curve (Bennike *et al.* 2021), the study area was subject to a rapid shore-level rise of approximately 8 mm a⁻¹ on average

in the period from ~12 to 8 calibrated (cal.) ka BP (BP: before present, 1950) and relative sea-level reached a maximum at around 6 cal. ka BP. Since then, relative sea-level has decreased towards present-day mean sea-level (Fig. 2). The present-day coastal setting of the study area and the location within a narrow embayment suggest that the area was significantly influenced by these past relative sea-level changes. Hence, the geological record of the bay likely documents a dynamic landscape evolution in response to changes in sea-level and sediment supply.

In this study, we present a detailed analysis of the depositional succession in Kalø Bay to reconstruct the palaeolandscape evolution, and to investigate the impact of sea-level changes by analysing variations in the depositional and erosional processes in the embayment. The objective was to assess and discuss the response and sensitivity of coastal embayments to rising sea-level within the framework of future projected accelerating sea-level rise.

Geological and environmental setting

The study area is situated in the coastal embayment Kalø Bay, which is surrounded by a comparatively high topography landscape named Mols Bjerge (Fig. 1A). The landscape around Mols Bjerge was largely formed by glacial processes, showing a geomorphology characterized by subglacial valleys (tunnel valleys), marginal moraines, mega-scale glacial lineations (MSGs), hummocky topography, drumlins and outwash plains (Fig. 1A–C; GEUS 2022). Many of these glacial features were formed in relation to the main ice-advance during the LGM from the north-east 23–21 cal. ka BP (Houmark-Nielsen 2010; Larsen *et al.* 2017). Land seismic investigations in Mols Bjerge, however, also show that the present-day high topography in part was controlled by older topography at the Top Chalk (Top Danien) surface in the core of Mols Bjerge (Clausen *et al.* 2017). The distinctly curved and hilly landscape around Kalø Bay (Fig. 1A, B) formed as marginal push moraines during the active stage of the Young Baltic Ice Advance 18 cal. ka BP (e.g. Jensen *et al.* 2002; Houmark-Nielsen 2010; Larsen *et al.* 2017; Jørgensen 2024, 2025). Following Larsen *et al.* (2017), Kalø Bay together with Ebeltoft Bay (Fig. 1A), comprise the topographical low-lying centres of two former ice lobes. Sandersen & Jørgensen (2016) report a NE–SW-

oriented, buried (30–110 m below the sea floor), Quaternary valley in the central part of Kalø Bay (Fig. 1C), yet do not discuss the possible age. During the deglaciation, approximately 17–16 cal. ka BP, the ice lobes recessed and left behind a landscape dominated by stagnant ice that led to the formation of kettleholes and kames in the region (Houmark-Nielsen 2010; Larsen *et al.* 2017).

The landscape around Kalø Bay also comprises raised marine sediments and former straits and fjords (e.g., Kolind Strait and Stubbe Lake) (Fig. 1A), a result of glacio-isostatic rebound that surpassed the global sea-level rise after the last deglaciation. The present-day coastline around Kalø Bay includes various coastal types, such as sedimentary cliffs consisting of till and sandy beaches (e.g., Geocenter Denmark 2021). In some cases, these coastal landscapes can be traced directly into the marine realm where, for instance, till forms parts of the present-day sea floor (Fig. 1B; GEUS 2020). Most of the sea floor in Kalø Bay is, however, characterized by mud and fine-grained sand (Fig. 1B). The average water depths in Kalø Bay are 5–15 m, increasing up to 20–25 m in a submarine channel that meanders towards Knebel Bay (Fig. 1A). The present-day hydrodynamics in Kalø Bay are prone to fetch-limited wave processes that cause local wave-driven longshore coastal features, like spits (Fig. 1C). The area is micro-tidal with a maximum tidal range of 0.3 m (Geocenter Denmark 2021) and is generally dominated by outwards-directed surface currents (e.g. Larsen *et al.* 2018).

Data and methods

Data for this study comprise high-resolution reflection seismic data in the form of subbottom profiles and sediment cores (Fig. 3). The data were collected as part of student teaching cruises to Kalø Bay in the years 2018–2024 using Aarhus University's research vessel *Aurora*.

Subbottom profiles

The subbottom profiles were acquired using a narrow-beam (beam width $\pm 2^\circ$) parametric subbottom profiler from Innomar of the model SES2000-Compact that is hull-mounted on R/V *Aurora*. Survey acquisition speed varied between 4 and 8 knots. Navigation input to the subbottom profiler came from an Applanix POSMV320

Fig. 1. A. Hill-shaded elevation model of the study area in Kattegat, Denmark (GEUS 2023, 2025a) showing the relatively high topography of Mols Bjerge surrounding Kalø Bay and Ebeltoft Bay. A submarine channel in Kalø Bay defines the main bathymetric feature of the bay. The inset map shows the study area (red star) in relation to northern Europe. B. Hill-shaded elevation model overlain with surface geology (1:25 000) (Andersen *et al.* 2024; GEUS 2025b) and sea floor sediments (Leth & Larsen 2014; GEUS 2020) showing a dominance of glacial and proglacial sediments onshore and a muddy sea floor in Kalø Bay. The blue polygons show the occurrence of shallow gas accumulations in Kalø Bay (this study) and Aarhus Bay (Flury *et al.* 2016). C. Geomorphology around Kalø Bay (GEUS 2022) is dominated by marginal moraines, till plains and hummocky terrain. Also shown are two buried Quaternary valleys from Sandersen & Jørgensen (2016).

Fig. 2. Stratigraphic framework for the mapped units in this study with interpreted environments. The shore-level curve is from Bennike *et al.* (2021). YD = Younger Dryas stadial; B-A = Bølling-Allerød interstadial.

system with RTK (Real-Time Kinematic) linked GPS (Global Positioning System) positions and an IMU (Inertial Measurement Unit) motion sensor to correct for ship movement, in particular the roll, pitch and heave. The subbottom profiler has a fixed primary high frequency of 100 kHz and generates secondary low-frequency signals between 2 and 15 kHz. Data were acquired using a recording length window between 16 and 25 m (21 and 33 ms two-way-travel-time (TWT)) and a low-frequency signal of 10 kHz that ensured good penetration in some areas. Generally, the imaging depths varied from 1 to 20 ms TWT (~1–16 m) below the sea floor depending on the geology, with low penetration in areas where tills are exposed at the sea floor and large penetration in areas with thick successions of softer deposits like marine mud. The 10 kHz signal further ensured a high vertical resolution of ~4 cm, estimated as a quarter of the dominant pulse-length using the 10 kHz frequency and a sediment velocity of 1600 m s⁻¹ (cf. Cotterill *et al.* 2017).

The data set consists of 330 subbottom profiles of varying lengths acquired in a ~41 km² large area within Kalø Bay and in the inlet to the bay (Fig. 3). Due to the draught of the vessel, the subbottom profiles were acquired in areas with water depths over 6 m and thus shallower areas close to the shore were not investigated. The spacing between the subbottom profiles is irregular and varies between 10 and 1000 m. The overall quality of the subbottom profiles is good due to calm weather during most of the survey days and little interference with other acoustic systems that run simultaneously dur-

ing the cruises (e.g. single channel sparker seismics and multibeam echo-sounding—not used for this study). Data processing was kept to a minimum and included only slight smoothing and minor TWT mistie corrections to correlate data from the various years and compensate for minor tidal variations. The signal penetration depth is reduced in areas with shallow gas accumulations (likely biogenic) (Fig. 1B) that causes a blanking effect on the acoustic data (e.g. Jensen & Bennike 2009; Flury *et al.* 2016; Boldreel & Pedersen 2024). The S&P Global Kingdom software (version 2022) was used for subbottom profile analyses. Surfaces were picked with semi-automatic modes using the basic principles for seismic facies mapping and seismic stratigraphy and linking those to depositional environments (e.g. Mitchum *et al.* 1977; Badley 1985; Posamentier *et al.* 2022; Newton *et al.* 2024). Gridding of the picked surfaces used the FlexGridding algorithm with a cell size of 10 × 10 m, minimum curvature level and a midway smoothing level. Each grid was constrained laterally by a polygon mask that was digitized to encompass the area of the picked surface. The used gridding algorithm and parameters produced realistic maps of the picked surfaces, however with some grid artefacts still visible. For seismic-to-core-tie and depth conversions, a sediment propagation sound velocity of 1600 m s⁻¹ (cf. Cotterill *et al.* 2017) and a sound velocity through water of 1500 m s⁻¹ was used.

Sediment cores

The sediment cores comprise four gravity cores (AU18-MG-05G, AU18-MG-09G, AU19-MG-07G and AU19-MG-12G shortened in the text and figures to 05G, 07G, 09G and 12G), one Rumohr Lot core (AU23-TUE-R1, shortened to R1) and information from one vibrocore (DGU-561022.1, shortened to 561022.1) (Table 1). Data on the latter are available from the Danish National Well Database Jupiter (Jupiter 2023). After retrieval, the cores were cut into 1-m-long sections, split lengthwise and described visually. The descriptions included lithological units, grain-size variations, colour changes, shell content and sedimentary structures. The archive halves were photographed and scanned with an ITRAX core scanner at Aarhus University, providing high-quality photographs through line scans. Selected cores were sampled for radiocarbon dating using shells and plant remains. The samples were dated using AMS (accelerator mass spectrometry) ¹⁴C dating at laboratories in Aarhus, Denmark and Zurich, Switzerland. The ¹⁴C dates were calibrated to calendar ages using calibration curves INTCAL20 (Reimer *et al.* 2020) for terrestrial samples and MARINE20 (Heaton *et al.* 2020) with $\Delta R = -234 \pm 61$ years (Fischer & Olsen 2021) for marine samples (Table 2).

Fig. 3. Overview of subbottom profiles (grey lines) and sediment cores (black dots) used in the study. Gravity core 05G and Rumohr Lot core R1 were both taken within the submarine channel, while gravity cores 07G and 09G were taken near the shallow-water area termed 'the Plate'. Bathymetry from EMODnet (2023) and hill-shaded elevation model from GEUS (2025a). The green lines show the position of profiles in Figs 4, 5, while purple lines show location of profiles used in Table 3.

Table 1. Sediment cores used in the study.

Core name	Easting ¹ (m)	Northing ¹ (m)	Latitude, °N	Longitude, °E	Water depth (m)	Core length (cm)	Coring technique	Year
AU18-MG-05G	589 800.9	6 233 847.6	56.2410	10.4489	12.5	510	Gravity	2018
AU18-MG-09G	587 860.7	6 233 227.0	56.2358	10.4174	9.9	375	Gravity	2018
AU19-MG-07G	587 547.1	6 233 414.4	56.2375	10.4125	9.8	370	Gravity	2019
AU19-MG-12G	587 738.7	6 234 336.0	56.2458	10.4158	10.5	520	Gravity	2019
AU23-TUE-R1	587 519.4	6 235 600.7	56.2572	10.4127	13.6	75.5	Rumohr Lot	2023
DGU-561022.1	585 445.0	6 235 054.0	56.2526	10.3790	13.1	900	Vibro	2000

¹UTM Zone 32N, ETRS89.

Results and discussion

Sedimentary units in the study area

From the subbottom profiles, we have mapped four units (Unit I–IV) that comprise the succession visible

on the profiles (Figs 3–5). The units are defined by specific seismic facies (SF) (Table 3). Some facies, such as the parallel continuous facies (SF1), can be observed in more units, while other facies only occur locally, restricted to one specific unit (e.g. SF4). In addition to the seismic facies description, we use

Table 2. Radiocarbon dates from Kalø Bay used in this study.

Core name	Latitude, °N	Longitude, °E	Laboratory number	Sample depth in core (cm)	Material	Age ¹ (¹⁴ C a BP)	Calibrated age ² (cal. a BP)	Source
AU18-MG-09G	56.2358	10.4174	AAR-30089	369	Twig	8256±41	9032–9412	Bennike <i>et al.</i> (2021)
			AAR-30088	373	Twig	8219±46	9022–9399	Bennike <i>et al.</i> (2021)
AU23-TUE-R1	56.2572	10.4127	ETH-142497.2.1	12.5	Shell fragment	−982±72	NA	This study
			ETH-142497.2.1	41	Shell (<i>Macoma balthica</i>)	860±64	315–687	This study
			ETH-142497.2.1	70	Shell (<i>Macoma balthica</i>)	7710±79	7977–8465	This study

¹Radiocarbon dates in conventional ¹⁴C years BP (before present = 1950; Stuiver & Polach 1977).

²Ages calibrated to calendar years BP (2 sigma) using calibration curves INTCAL20 (Reimer *et al.* 2020) for terrestrial samples (09G) and MARINE20 (Heaton *et al.* 2020) with $\Delta R = -234 \pm 61$ years (Fischer & Olsen 2021) for marine samples (R1).

the sediment cores to describe the lithology of the units.

Unit I. – Unit I comprises the lowermost visible succession on the subbottom profiles (e.g. Figs 4, 5). The top of the unit is mostly a high-amplitude, prolonged, continuous to discontinuous reflection that can be mapped in the entire study area (e.g. Table 3, seismic facies (SF) 3). The top of the unit is in some places erosional (e.g. Fig. 4A), and other places conformable (Figs 4, 5). The variable nature of the Top Unit I surface can be correlated with the different seismic facies observed in Unit I, ranging from parallel stratified (SF1) (Fig. 4A), transparent mounded (SF2) (Fig. 4A) to chaotic (SF3) facies (Table 3). The Top Unit I surface is mostly conformable when it overlies the transparent mounded and chaotic facies of Unit I, while it is mostly erosional when overlying the parallel stratified facies of Unit I (Fig. 4A). The surface defines a distinct palaeotopography (Fig. 6A) consisting of 700 to 900 m wide elevated curved ridges towards the north and east. The ridges are separated by deep (up to 13 m) and wide (up to 800 m) elongated to semi-circular depressions. In the central part of Kalø Bay, the Top Unit I surface shows a shallower and wider (up to 1900 m) deepening that extends southward in a channelized manner (Fig. 6A). In the channelized depression, Unit I shows a truncated parallel stratified facies indicating erosion of the unit at this location. Within the curved ridges, the Top Unit I surface is typically of high-amplitude, overlying a chaotic succession (SF3), which occasionally show low-amplitude inclined reflections (Fig. 4B, D). The chaotic facies (SF3) of Unit I is furthermore observed at places where the Top Unit I surface coincides with the present-day sea floor (i.e. where Unit I is exposed to the sea). In these areas, the sea floor sediment map (Fig. 1B) indicates till.

The transparent, mounded structures (SF2) of Unit I occur in two areas in the centre of Kalø Bay (Fig. 6A, H). Farthest south, the mounds are 2.5–5.5 m high, approximately 200 m wide and amalgamated over a distance of

~2.5 km, while in the north, they reach a height of 8.5 m, a width of 200–400 m and are amalgamated over a distance of ~2.1 km. There are occasionally some internal reflections of very-low amplitude within the mounds (Fig. 4A, Table 3—SF2). In two smaller areas, Unit I is composed of an up to 3 m thick flat-topped positive topographic feature, with inclined (1.5–2°), prograding climbing to hummocky reflection patterns towards either west–south-west or north-east (Figs 4B, 6H).

For the parallel stratified facies (SF1), which generally occur in the central and southern parts of Kalø Bay (Fig. 6H), the maximum thickness imaged in the data is 12 ms TWT (~9 m). The total thickness of Unit I cannot be determined because the base of the unit was not imaged.

Only the DGU-561022.1 vibrocore reached into Unit I (Figs 4B, 7A). The core shows that Unit I at this position mainly consists of sand, except for a 25 cm thick silt layer near the top of the unit (Fig. 7A). In the subbottom profile at the vibrocore location (Fig. 4B), Unit I is characterized by low-amplitude inclined (0.5–1°) sub-parallel reflections.

Unit II. – Unit II lies directly above Unit I and comprises four subunits defined by distinct seismic facies types (e.g. Fig. 4C). Subunits IIa, IIb and IIc have limited lateral extent occurring only within the central deepening of the Top Unit I surface and towards the south. Subunit IIa comprises a 0.5–1.5 m thick succession with low-amplitude parallel to subparallel reflections, while subunits IIb and IIc in most places, are characterized by a distinct wavy to sigmoid prograding reflection pattern with discrete crests and troughs (SF4, Table 3) (Fig. 4C). Both subunits (IIb and IIc) are around 0.5 m thick. Occasionally, they reach up to 1 m in thickness particularly towards the south, where the subunits occur on the western side of the transparent mounds of Unit I (Fig. 6H). The distance between the crests varies from 5 to 30 m. Generally, the sigmoid prograding pattern appears to prograde in a northern to north-eastern

Table 3. Main seismic facies. See Fig. 3 for location of profiles.

Seismic facies (SF)	Reflection pattern	Interpretation	Example	Occur in
SF1	Parallel to subparallel, high to medium amplitude, continuous, onlapping to divergent	Low-energy (glacio) lacustrine to brackish-marine infill sediments		Units I and II, IV
SF2	Transparent mounded	Esker complex		Unit I
SF3	Chaotic to transparent with prolonged top	Till		Unit I
SF4	Wavy to sigmoid prograding	Near-shore bars		Unit II
SF5	Confined prograding, divergent or onlapping	Channel infill		Units II and IV
SF6	Parallel low-amplitude to transparent	Marine hemipelagic infill sediments		Unit III
SF7	Prograding downlapping, to aggrading clinofolds	Bottom current deposits		Units IV and III
SF8	Hummocky to wavy with internal incisions	Shallow marine to coastal deposits		Unit IV

Fig. 4. Subbottom profiles showing the seismic facies variations across the units. A. Long profile showing the transparent mounds and truncated parallel stratified facies of Unit I. The internal subdivision of Unit II is marked by the Top subunit IIc surface. Unit III and Unit IV show low-amplitude facies. B. Profile showing the seismic tie to the 561022.1 core as well as various seismic facies within Unit I. The red surfaces in Unit II mark erosional surfaces. C. Profile showing the four distinct subunits of Unit II including the prograding sigmoid facies of subunit IIb. Also shown is the tie to the R1 core. D. Profile intersecting the curved ridges of Unit I towards the NE. In the WSW part of the profile, Unit II is thick with a clear internal erosive surface (red), it fills the topography of the Top Unit I surface. Towards the ENE, Unit II only partly fills the elongated depressions between the curved ridges, and these areas are therefore further deprecipitated for the overlying Unit III. Black star highlights an area with a steep low-amplitude zone. E. Profile showing the hummocky to wavy seismic facies of Unit IV, as well as the low-amplitude to transparent facies of Unit III. Unit II shows a larger internal incision (red surface). See Fig. 3 for location of profiles and Fig. 7 for explanation of colours used for the cores.

Fig. 5. Subbottom profiles showing the seismic facies variations across the units. A–C. and F. Seismic-to-core-ties of the four gravity cores; for explanation of colours, see Fig. 7. D. Profile perpendicular to the submarine channel at the inlet to Kalø Bay showing the prograding to aggrading reflection pattern. E. Profile perpendicular to the present-day submarine channel showing the prograding to aggrading and downlapping reflections within Unit IV south of the channel and a marked erosion of Unit III north of the channel (erosional truncations highlighted by black half-arrows). The inset profile highlights how steep zones of low-amplitude reflections (highlighted with black stars) arise from inclined and curved bedding associated with the erosional surface internally of subunit II. See Fig. 3 for location of profiles.

Fig. 6. Structure and thickness maps of the observed units. A–D. Structures maps in depth (TWT and metres) below sea surface of Top Unit I, Top Unit II, Top Unit III and the sea floor (Top Unit IV). E–G. Thickness maps (TWT and metres) of Units II–IV. Depocentres of Unit IV (G) marked by DP1 and DP2. H. Distribution of key seismic facies in Unit I and II superimposed with the outline of shallow gas accumulations. The top of the gas accumulations occurs mainly within Units II and III, but the blanking influences all the underlying units. Black dots show locations of boreholes.

direction (Fig. 4C, Table 3—SF4). In areas where subunits IIa–c are thick, there are occasionally a poorer signal penetration of the underlying units (Unit I) (e.g. Fig. 4A). This most likely indicates that the sediments of subunits IIa–c are rather hard, such as sand, gravel or till, hindering the subbottom profiler instrument to image the succession below.

The main facies of Unit II, which is observed throughout the study area, is linked to subunit II d that has a draping parallel to divergent reflection pattern (SF1) of high to medium amplitude. Internally, subunit II d is often characterized by distinct high-amplitude erosional surfaces that locally define buried incisions of various dimensions (e.g. Figs 4B, D, E, 5B, C, E, F). The infill facies of these buried incisions are characterized as confined prograding to divergent (SF5, Table 3). The buried incisions are more distinct towards the shores of Kalø Bay and appear well developed close to ‘the Plate’ (a shallow-water area in the bay—for location see Fig. 1), while they are absent in the central and deepest parts of Kalø Bay. In places, subunit II d appears deformed and faulted with steep ($\sim 10^\circ$) low-amplitude to transparent zones (e.g. Fig. 5E, F—black stars). However, reducing the vertical exaggeration on the subbottom profiles reveal these zones to be linked either to the erosional surfaces internally of subunit II d or to inclined or curved low-amplitude reflections (see inset profile in Fig. 5E). Taken together, the internal erosional surfaces and the deformed pattern of subunit II d indicate a relatively dynamic depositional environment and subunit II d likely comprises several locally deposited entities.

The top of Unit II is marked by the transition to the overlying low-amplitude to transparent Unit III. This boundary is most often gradual, but occasionally it appears to be erosional, typically towards the shores of Kalø Bay (e.g. Fig. 5E). The surface defines a palaeotopography (Fig. 6B) similar to that of Top Unit I, but with a lower elevation. Unit II has varying thicknesses, typically between 2 and 6 m, reflecting that the unit is mainly infilling the topography defined by the Top Unit I surface (Fig. 6E). Noteworthy, the central deepening of the Top Unit I surface appears to be completely infilled by Unit II. The maximum thickness of Unit II is around 8 m, while the unit is thin (<1 m) in other areas of Kalø Bay (Fig. 6E).

All four gravity cores reached into subunit II d (Fig. 5A–D) and the seismic-to-core ties show that the subunit in the top is composed of laminated clay with no or few marine mollusc shells (Fig. 7C, J), except for a few marked shell layers (e.g. Fig. 7D, G). Gravity core 12G, which is located most centrally in Kalø Bay, comprises the most distinct and deepest layers of marine cockle shells (Fig. 7D) that occur below the succession of laminated clay.

Gravity cores 07G and 09G were taken close to ‘the Plate’ and in areas showing buried incisions in subunit

II d (Fig. 5B, C). Both cores terminate at a few cm thick sand layer overlying peat (Fig. 7F, H). Twigs from the peat in core 09G were dated to the Early Holocene (Table 2). Within the incisions, the cores generally show a slightly laminated, light grey clay with a downwards increasing content of organic matter and plant remains (Fig. 7F, H).

Unit III. – Unit III is generally characterized by a low-amplitude to transparent facies (SF6, Table 3), which is distinctly different from the underlying high-amplitude stratified Unit II (Figs 4, 5). Embedded in the low-amplitude facies, some areas show abundant diffraction hyperbolas indicative of reflections from point objects (e.g. Figs 4D, 5F). Unit III is mainly associated with a few distinct depocentres, some of which correlate with the depocentres from Unit II (Fig. 6F). Furthermore, Unit III shows a significant depocentre related to the southern channelized depression in the Top Unit I and Top Unit II surfaces. Here, the seismic facies are composed of prograding to aggrading reflections (SF7, Table 3) (Fig. 5D). The maximum thickness is 11 m. The top of the unit is marked by the transition to the overlying Unit IV, which generally shows higher amplitude reflections (Figs 4, 5). The Top Unit III surface is mostly erosional (Fig. 4A, D) but is also conformable and associated with a gradual change from Unit III to IV in places (Fig. 5D). Bioturbation in the gravity cores attests to an apparent gradual transition from Unit III to Unit IV (Fig. 7E, G, I). In the areas of the present-day submarine channel, Unit III is eroded as clearly indicated by reflection truncations and is completely missing in places (Fig. 5E). The Top Unit III surface shows a flatter topography (Fig. 6C) compared to the Top Unit I and Top Unit II surfaces, indicating that most of the depressions from the earlier stages were infilled. An exception to this is the channelized depression at the southern inlet to Kalø Bay, which in part correlates with the present-day sea floor channel. Comparing the position of the channelized depression in the Top Units I, II and III surfaces and the sea floor (Fig. 6A–D), shows that the depression narrows from ~ 800 m in Top Units I and II to ~ 200 m in the sea floor surface, as it laterally migrates towards the east.

The gravity cores show that Unit III consist of light grey clay with varying content of marine mollusc shells, and varying degree of bioturbation (Fig. 7). Unit III was also sampled by the R1 core taken at the base of the present-day submarine channel where Units IV and III are both very thin (Fig. 4C). Unit III shows the same light grey clay with scattered shells as in the gravity cores. A dated sample from Unit III has a Mid-Holocene age (Table 2).

Unit IV. – Unit IV is the uppermost and youngest unit. It comprises a variety of seismic facies, ranging from stratified (sub)parallel medium amplitude reflections (SF1)

Fig. 7. A. Core logs showing main lithologies and grain size, sedimentary structures and content of shells and plant remains. The dashed coloured lines represent the position of the seismic surfaces at the cores, based either on the seismic-to-core ties or depth-converted TWT for the surfaces below the total depth of the cores. B–J. Selected core photos showing various lithofacies linked to the seismic units. Please note the colour difference between the gravity cores (C–J) and the Rumohr Lot core (B). Yellow boxes in B and H indicate the positions of radiocarbon-dated samples (Table 2).

(Figs 4C, 5F), hummocky and wavy (SF8, Table 3) (Fig. 4E), to prograding and aggrading (SF7) with distinct downlaps (SF7) (Fig. 5D, E). The prograding to aggrading facies occur in relation to the present-day submarine channel where two distinct depocentres (DP1 and DP2 in Fig. 6G) can be observed, showing respectively northward (DP1) (Fig. 5E) and eastward (DP2) prograding facies (Fig. 5D). The undulating hummocky to wavy facies (SF8) are particularly well-developed towards the area of ‘the Plate’ (Figs 4E, 5C). Several internal erosion surfaces furthermore define relatively wide incisions (up to 50 m wide) (Table 3—SF5).

The top of the unit (present-day sea floor) is a high-amplitude continuous reflection. Generally, the sea floor is flat compared to the underlying surfaces, except for the submarine channel and a few smaller tributaries (Fig. 6D). In the north, the submarine channel has a depth of 3–5 m and is typically 150–250 m wide, while it reaches depths and widths up to 10 and 200 m, respectively, towards the south (Fig. 6D). The channel appears to terminate in the smaller Knebel Bay.

Unit IV has varying thickness from 0 to 9 m with the greatest thicknesses related to the two depocentres (Fig. 6G). The cores in the submarine channel (R1 and 05G) show that the uppermost part of Unit IV is composed of gyttja here (Fig. 7A, B), while Unit IV in the other cores situated away from the submarine channel (07G, 09G, 12G) consists of silty clay with few marine mollusc shells and shell fragments (Fig. 7). Based on the radiocarbon dates, the gyttja in R1 is deposited within the last few centuries (Table 2).

Chronology of the mapped units

The poor age control of the mapped units does not generally allow for a strong temporal resolution of the geological strata observed in Kalø Bay. However, the available ages of subunit II d (09G), the lower part of Unit III (R1) and the gyttja in Unit IV (R1) (Table 2) capture significant depositional changes that establish an overall chronology of the units together with the known lithologies and mapped seismic facies. None of the cores reach Unit I, so that no constraints are possible on the age of this unit. However, interpretation of the morphologies as presented in the following section, and the lithology that includes till where Unit I is at the sea floor, suggest that this unit mainly consists of glacial deposits.

Hence, we propose an overall chronology of the mapped units: We suggest that Unit I represents glacial deposits, most likely associated with MIS 2, Unit II

encompasses latest Pleistocene to Early and early Mid-Holocene deposits, Unit III deposits are from the Mid-Holocene and Unit IV covers Late Holocene and recent deposits (Fig. 2).

The various nature of the seismic facies, particularly for Unit I, Unit II and Unit IV, furthermore, suggests that these units either formed over a considerable amount of time (Unit I) or that they captured relatively rapidly changing or dynamic depositional environments with multiple processes acting at once (Units II and IV). In the following, we discuss the main interpretations for the units based on our observations.

Geological interpretation of seismic facies in Unit I–IV

Unit I. – The best indication of a glacial origin of Unit I is the correlation with till on the sea floor. In these cases, we observe the Top Unit I surface as the distinct prolonged reflection on top of a chaotic to transparent facies (SF3). We therefore interpret these uppermost seismic facies of Unit I to represent till deposited in relation to the Young Baltic ice lobe in the bay. Similar interpretations of seismic facies associated with tills have been presented in many studies from the inner Danish waters (e.g. Bendixen *et al.* 2017; Andresen *et al.* 2021; Bennike *et al.* 2021). The topography of the Top Unit I surface further shows curved ridges, which are morphologically similar, but of much smaller scale to the Mols Bjerger present-day hilly terrain. Within the ridges, we observe the same seismic facies (SF3) of Unit I indicative of till. We propose that the ridges constitute terminal moraines formed either as push moraines during ice lobe advance or more likely as recessional moraines during stillstand and melting of ice from the area.

The parallel, stratified, occasionally deformed and often erosional truncated facies (SF1) of Unit I occurs below the prolonged Top Unit I surface and hence must be associated with older deposits. Unfortunately, we do not have data on the lithology of these stratified deposits, but the seismic facies indicate water-lain deposits from a low-energy environment, that is, with low-energetic wave conditions and without tide, such as found in glaciomarine or glaciolacustrine settings (e.g. Vardy *et al.* 2010; Hjelstuen *et al.* 2018; Kurjanski *et al.* 2020). The seismic facies is comparable to nearby lateglacial successions from the Kattegat interpreted as marine sediments from the Yoldia Sea (e.g. Leth & Novak 2010; Bendixen *et al.* 2013, 2015, 2017), as well as stratified glaciolacustrine successions from the southern Baltic Sea (Baltic Ice Lake deposits, e.g. Jensen *et al.* 2017). We generally

observe these seismic facies centrally, within the deepest parts of Kalø Bay (Fig. 6H) and suggest that the associated sediments represent glaciomarine or glaciolacustrine clay and silt. Ice-rafted-debris (IRD) is a typical feature in glaciomarine and glaciolacustrine settings, showing up as point scatters (diffractions) in unmigrated seismic profiles. We do not, however, observe any such diffractions in Unit I and this may indicate that the lake or marine sediments formed at a distance to the ice margin, that is, in a proglacial setting. With our current data, it is difficult to ascertain whether the stratified facies of Unit I represent lateglacial marine deposits from the Yoldia Sea, or older (glacio-) lacustrine sediments. The Yoldia Sea expanded into the southern Kattegat region after the Young Baltic Ice retreated from the area at around 17–16 cal. ka BP (e.g. Jensen *et al.* 2002; Houmark-Nielsen & Kjær 2003; Larsen *et al.* 2009; Bendixen *et al.* 2015). Although there are no records in the literature of the Yoldia Sea reaching Kalø Bay, Vangkilde-Pedersen *et al.* (2025) mapped the thickness of lateglacial deposits in the Kattegat, showing localized depocentres in the inner parts of Aarhus Bay. It is therefore not unlikely that the Yoldia Sea extended into Kalø Bay as well. We do, however, favour a glaciolacustrine (and older) interpretation of the stratified facies in Unit I, because of the occurrence below the Top Unit I surface, which we correlate with till, and occurrence below other features (e.g. the transparent mounds) in Unit I which we also interpret as glacial features (see below). Towards the west, core 561022.1 shows sandy facies in Unit I that correlate with subparallel clinoform reflections, which appears to be time-equivalent to the parallel stratified facies (e.g. Fig. 4B). We suggest that the sandy, prograding clinoforms were formed in a glaciofluvial delta or a shoreline advancing into a proglacial lake (e.g. Patruno & Helland-Hansen 2018; McGlue *et al.* 2023). The clinoform topset or delta brink elevation (21–22 ms TWT) suggests that the palaeo-lake-level was ~17 m below present-day mean sea-level.

The distinct transparent mounds in Unit I occur above the parallel stratified facies (Fig. 4A) centrally in Kalø Bay (Fig. 6H) with a generally N–S-elongation and kinks that follow the main architecture of the bay. Given the characteristic morphology with amalgamations of multiple mounds, as well as the dimensions of the mounds, we propose that they represent short esker complexes formed subglacially, when meltwater channels below the ice were filled with meltwater deposits (cf. Brennan 2000; Storrar *et al.* 2015). That would imply a relatively coarse-grained infill (cf. Brennan 2000), which in turn could give the observed acoustic signature with a high-amplitude reflection at the top and a transparent infill. Alternative interpretations could include drumlins, where basal sediments below the ice were deformed and modulated into elongated triangular wedges (e.g. Stokes *et al.* 2011; Stokes 2017), or kames (e.g. Evans *et al.* 2016) forming either parallel to the ice front or in

a landscape with bodies of stagnant ice. Given the amalgamated nature of the mounds and the general but not streamlined N–S elongation, we find eskers to be a more likely interpretation compared to drumlins that are normally more strictly elongated (Stokes *et al.* 2011). Observing the dimensions of the mounds, they are furthermore comparable to eskers reported from other studies (e.g. Thomas & Montague 1997; Ottesen *et al.* 2008; Feldens *et al.* 2013; Storrar *et al.* 2015; Kirkham *et al.* 2024). Kames form in a stagnant ice landscape, and would likely have been found in Kalø Bay after the retreat of the Young Baltic Ice. There are reports of kames west of Kalø Bay (Fig. 1C) and at many other places in Denmark, but most often the kame morphology is associated with a wider hummocky terrain consisting of distinct hills. This is not what we observe for the transparent mounds. The elongated nature along with the known tunnel valley north of the bay (Fig. 1C; Smed 1981; GEUS 2022) and the subglacial valley of Sandersen & Jørgensen (2016) furthermore favours a subglacial origin.

Within Unit I, the prograding climbing to hummocky reflections (Fig. 4B) occur in two places farther north than the transparent mounds (Fig. 6H). Here, the Top Unit I surface is generally at shallower depth and the reflections appear to be associated with sediments younger than the transparent mounds. Compared to the prograding clinoforms interpreted as deltaic or shoreline deposits above, these prograding reflections are steeper, show a hummocky pattern in places and define a distinct positive flat-topped topographic feature (Fig. 4B). The reflection pattern suggests deposition in a locally higher energy environment, such as an ice contact delta (e.g. Kurjanski *et al.* 2021), a glaciofluvial landscape dominated by stagnant ice and formation of kames or a migrating shallow-water sand bar (e.g. Lericolais *et al.* 2007; Fruergaard *et al.* 2018).

Unit II. – For the lower parts of Unit II, we do not have any constraints on the lithology, and we therefore consider more interpretations for the observed seismic facies. One interpretation could be that the lower parts of Unit II (subunits IIa, b, c) represent a deglaciation succession, consisting mainly of sandy facies deposited during melt-out as sand sheets in a glaciofluvial setting or as prograding delta-like features at the edges of local ponds or lakes (e.g. Kurjanski *et al.* 2020, 2021). Such a sandy facies interpretation fits well with the observed poorer signal penetration of the underlying Unit I in areas where subunits IIa, b and c are thicker (e.g. Fig. 4A). During the later postglacial marine transgression, this deglaciation succession would have been subject to intense reworking by shallow marine processes.

An alternative interpretation could be that subunits IIa, b and c represent postglacial sediments formed in a shallow marine setting. Subunits IIb and IIc show the distinct way to sigmoidal, prograding pattern (SF4) with well-

defined crests and troughs. None of the cores reach the subunits, but the reflection pattern and the dimensions allow for interpretation as near-shore/swash bars or perhaps beach ridges (e.g. Lindhorst *et al.* 2008; Fruergaard *et al.* 2018) formed by waves in a shallow marine environment. The palaeo-water depth in the bay at this time would have varied depending on the location in the bay. The depth to the top of the bars varies from 15 m to 20 m below the present-day sea surface. Although we do not know the precise age of subunit IIb and IIc, a shallow-water marine environment interpretation would indicate a postglacial formation during the early stages of the marine inundation, suggested to be around 9 cal. ka BP in Aarhus Bay (Rasmussen *et al.* 2020; Bennike *et al.* 2021). From the shore-level curve (Fig. 2), the sea-level was 15–20 m below present-day sea-level at 9 cal. ka BP, matching shallow palaeo-water depths of around 0–5 m during formation of the bars. The bars occur in a restricted area coinciding with the western and northern sides of the eskers in Unit I (Fig. 6H) and appear to migrate over and up the eskers (Fig. 4A, C). We therefore propose that the formation and preservation of the bars was largely controlled by the eskers. The wave-generated near-shore bars were likely formed in the early stages of the marine inundation during rapidly rising sea-level and transgression, as structures migrating towards the palaeo-coastline which at the time was positioned at the eskers. The steeper topography and volume of the eskers would have hindered the coastline to rapidly adjust landwards during the transgression. This in turn facilitated local, deeper water settings and the accommodation space for the near-shore bars to form. With continued rapid sea-level rise, the bars drowned and became inactive. Conditions were furthermore favourable for preservation of the bars. The two subunits are very similar but differ slightly in bar height and size. This shift likely reflects local changes in sediment input and water level providing different conditions for the wave-driven sediment transport in the system. Considering the small area of Kalø Bay, the relatively low water level and the sheltered position in Kattegat, we do not find it likely that tidal or barotropic flows influenced the formation of the bars (Reynaud & Dalrymple 2012; Dalrymple 2023). Any tidal influence would have been very small and the main agent in the bay was likely waves rather than currents. Thus, the parallel stratified subunit IIc likely represents deposits from a calmer, non-coastal setting occurring as the area was transgressed and gradually became fully marine. This is supported by the occurrence of marine shells in subunit IIc (Fig. 7D).

Unit III. – The transparent seismic facies of Unit III is interpreted to represent homogenous marine clay deposits, which is supported by the cores showing some marine mollusc shells within the clay of Unit III and bioturbation (Fig. 7). The diffraction hyperbolas are interpreted as originating from smaller stones embedded in the marine sediments. Stones may originate from erosion

of coastal cliffs with till and can in non-glacial settings be transported into deeper water during storms carried by macroalgae attached to the stones. An alternative interpretation could be that the diffractions originate as side swipe reflections from stones on the sea floor next to the sail line. In Kalø Bay, there are many places where the sea floor is stony, particularly close to the shore of till cliffs and in areas where till or other diamict are exposed to the sea and subject to winnowing of the fines.

Unit IV. – For Unit IV, the most distinct facies is the prograding to aggrading reflection pattern (SF7) observed in relation to the present-day submarine channel of Kalø Bay. These deposits show expected characteristics of a submarine meandering channel system with cut-bank erosion at the outer bends and point bar deposition (or lateral accretion) at the inner bends (Fig. 5E) (e.g. Abreu *et al.* 2003; Li & Gong 2016). Depending on definitions, the system could also be characterized as a submarine, bottom-current controlled deposit or a shallow-water contourite (e.g. Faugères *et al.* 1999; Rebesco *et al.* 2014; Jensen *et al.* 2017).

Within Unit IV, the hummocky to wavy reflection pattern (SF8) with internal incisions is best developed towards the shallower water area of ‘the Plate’. We interpret this seismic facies as resulting from a shallow-water environment where changing riverine input and wave-driven longshore sediment transport-controlled sedimentation, allowed for the high variability in deposition and erosion (Søe *et al.* 2018; van Kouwen *et al.* 2023). Temporal storm-induced currents (e.g. Swatridge *et al.* 2022) may further have affected the sedimentation and eroded the larger incisions.

Geological development of the study area after the last glaciation

With the above interpretations, the unit descriptions and the seismic facies variations, we present an eight-staged geological formation model for the study area after the LGM (Fig. 8). Because of limited chronological control of the depositional units, the temporal resolution of the model is inherently low and charged with a high uncertainty. The few control dates still indicate the overall timing, and the model thus serves as a good overview of the major changes in geological setting and depositional environment that has been recorded in the sediments of the bay.

Pleistocene stages (Stages 1–3). – During Stage 1 (Fig. 8A), Kalø Bay was yet to be overridden by the ice lobes of the Young Baltic Advance. The ice-sheet margin was, however, located close to the bay, and within the bay, we propose that a glaciolacustrine environment persisted with deposition of laminated clay and silt at the centre of a proglacial lake. Fine-grained sand at the shores of the lake formed a delta (Fig. 8A). The lake might have been

dammed towards the south by the Young Baltic ice lobe, but the lack of point scatters in the lake succession suggests that there are no IRDs in the lake sediments, which favours a proglacial rather than ice-marginal setting. The location and northward extent of the lake was likely controlled by the terrain left behind from the previous main ice advance over the area as well as the older Cenozoic topography. We do not have any age constraints on the proposed glaciolacustrine deposits of Unit I, but we suggest that Stage 1 occurred at around 20 cal. ka BP, between the main ice advance from the north-east (23–21 cal. ka BP) and the Young Baltic Advance (19–18 cal. ka BP) from the south (Larsen *et al.* 2017).

In Stage 2 (Fig. 8B), at approximately 19–18 cal. ka BP, the Young Baltic Ice Advance had progressed across Kalø Bay and Ebeltoft Bay and formed the Mols Bjerge morainal landscape (Houmark-Nielsen 2010). In Kalø Bay, the glacial advance succession is evidenced by several observations. The distinct angular unconformity at the top of the proglacial lake deposits from Stage 1, as well as the occasionally gently folded nature of the lake deposits, indicate that the Top Unit I surface marks a glacial erosional surface with some ice-bed erosion and deformation. The gentle deformation of the lake deposits (Fig. 4A) may further suggest that the lake sediments acted as a decollement during the ice advance, hindering intense deformation of the substratum. Instead, most of the deformational forces appear to have been expended in the areas of the present-day Mols Bjerge at the northernmost margin of the ice (Houmark-Nielsen 2010; Larsen *et al.* 2017). Subglacial valleys occur onshore west and north of Kalø Bay (Fig. 1C) (Smed 1981; GEUS 2022) and offshore centrally within the bay (Sandersen & Jørgensen 2016). In our shallow subsurface data, we do not see evidence for the valley described by Sandersen & Jørgensen (2016). However, based on the spatial correlation to the esker complexes, we suggest that a meltwater channel, most likely of the R-channel type incised into the basal ice (Röthlisberger 1972) formed in Kalø Bay during Stage 2. The position of this subglacial meltwater channel may have been guided by the deeper buried valley of Sandersen & Jørgensen (2016) and the former proglacial lake topography.

During the retreat of the ice from the area (Stage 3, Fig. 8C) ~17–16 cal. ka BP, the subglacial channel was filled with meltwater deposits and formed the eskers. At the same time, the retreating ice left behind curved recessional moraines, forming the distinct curvy and hilly landscape of Top Unit I in Kalø Bay (Fig. 6A). Furthermore, stagnant ice within Kalø Bay likely led to the

formation of a hummocky terrain with kettleholes and kames, similar to morphologies reported from the onshore areas close to the bay (e.g. Larsen *et al.* 2009; Houmark-Nielsen 2010). With time, such glacial depressions could have reinforced the hilly landscape in the bay.

Early Holocene stages (Stage 4a and 4b). – In Stage 4 which extends over a relatively long-time interval (~15–9 cal. ka BP), Kalø Bay was at first characterized by a glaciofluvial landscape with stagnant ice. In this landscape, the lowermost parts of Unit II were deposited as a deglaciation succession. Later, mires and lakes probably started to develop in the deepest glacial depressions in the northern parts of the bay. Comparable mires and lakes forming in the wider Aarhus Bay at around 10–9 cal. ka BP have been discussed by Rasmussen *et al.* (2020) and Bennike *et al.* (2021). The glacial depressions in the Top Unit I surface in Kalø Bay had varying elevations (Figs 4D, 6A). This probably facilitated a non-uniform lake formation and non-uniform lake infill across the bay. At around 9 cal. ka BP (Stage 4a) (Fig. 8D), the sea started to inundate the lowest-lying areas of the bay and subunits IIb and IIc were deposited in a shallow-water setting where wave-erosion and reworking of the deglaciation succession led to the formation of near-shore bars. Other parts of the bay remained lacustrine or terrestrial (Fig. 8D) and were only flooded at a later stage.

Subunit II d was deposited later in Stage 4 (~9–8.5 cal. ka BP). During this time, the relative sea-level continued to rise and the lakes in the northern parts of Kalø Bay probably became larger (Stage 4b, Fig. 8E), occupying more of the low topography areas, as has been suggested for the lakes in Aarhus Bay (Bennike *et al.* 2021). Similarly, the marine transgression would have inundated more areas in Kalø Bay. Core 07G and 09G both terminated in peat overlain by clay with abundant plant remains (Fig. 7A, F, H), which we associate with subunit II d (Fig. 5B, C). The plant remains suggest formation in a near-coastal or terrestrial setting, while the peat indicates a terrestrial environment with a close proximity of the water table. We therefore propose that subunit II d at these locations represent telmatic and limnic environments. In contrast, the layers with shells of marine molluscs throughout the laminated clay in subunit II d at core 12G (Fig. 7), indicate a brackish and marine influence in the central part of the bay. The laminations of subunit II d in core 12G and 05G further indicate a relatively low-energy and anoxic environment with few burrowing benthic invertebrates.

Fig. 8. Palaeogeographical maps showing the geological model for the study area. Dashed black line indicates the present-day coastline. A–C. Pleistocene glacial stages showing formation of glaciolacustrine deposits and esker complex as part of Unit I. D. Early Holocene stage showing lakes towards the north and shallow-water (marine-brackish) conditions farther south with formation of near-shore bars. E–G. Early to Mid-Holocene stages showing the gradual flooding of Kalø Bay. H. Late Holocene to present-day conditions in the bay showing the submarine channel. See text for further description.

Besides representing different environments, subunit II_d shows a high complexity with internal erosion surfaces (Fig. 5F), local incisions and vertical low-amplitude zones (Fig. 5E), some of which could arise from postdepositional deformation of the soft clays, perhaps due to minor sliding along a gently dipping basin floor (e.g. Fig. 5F, E). Subordinate units may therefore appear locally and correlation across the bay is non-trivial. Our seismic mapping shows that the marine inlet to the bay was restricted in width and depth (Fig. 6A) and likely functioned as a threshold (Fig. 8D, E), controlling the marine influx to the bay according to the subtle balance between eustatic sea-level rise, isostatic rebound and sedimentation. Similar thresholds have been described and discussed for the Great Belt in relation to both the drainage of the Ancylus Lake and the Littorina Transgression of the Baltic Sea (Jensen *et al.* 2005; Bendixen *et al.* 2015), as well as for the Limfjord in relation to the straits' western and northern North Sea connection (e.g. Andersen 1991). During the early stages of the marine inundation, Kalø Bay may have shifted between marine and brackish conditions until the final and permanent flooding—adding to the complexity of subunit II_d.

Mid- to Late Holocene marine stages (Stage 5a, 5b, 5c). – According to Rasmussen *et al.* (2020) and Bennike *et al.* (2021) who based their findings on calibrated radiocarbon-dated material, the marine inundation of Aarhus Bay took place around 9–8.5 cal. ka BP, when relative sea-level was around 15–10 m below present-day level (Fig. 2). As the sea entered and inundated larger areas of Kalø Bay (Fig. 8F, G), sedimentation changed to the fine-grained and more homogenous marine clay (Unit III) we associate with the Littorina sea-level high-stand facies (cf. Bendixen *et al.* 2015). The transition from Unit II to Unit III, marked by the Top Unit II surface represents another distinct marine flooding surface in the bay. In the deeper water areas of the bay, where the high-amplitude reflections of Unit II are gradually replaced by the transparent facies of Unit III (Fig. 5E), the inundation likely occurred with little erosion, while the shallower near-shore areas of the bay were more susceptible to erosion as documented by the truncated reflections in these areas (Fig. 5E). The abundant bioturbation in Unit III further suggests that oxic bottom conditions were established and maintained during the deposition of Unit III. This change in oxidation level may reflect an increased circulation in the bay as the sea-level rose.

At around 6 cal. ka BP (Stage 5b, Fig. 8G), the Littorina transgression reached its maximum extent with a relative sea-level around 2.5 m above present-day sea-level, flooding low-lying areas adjacent to Kalø Bay (Bennike *et al.* 2021). The higher sea-level probably facilitated increased water circulation in the bay, and we propose that a weak outward-flowing bottom current was also

initiated in the bay around this time. This current redistributed sediments in Unit III (and later Unit IV) and formed the distinct prograding to aggrading deposits (DP1 and DP2, Fig. 6G) and the channel in the bay.

With time, characterized by stable global sea-level, and continued glacio-isostatic rebound, the relative sea-level decreased and Kalø Bay became progressively smaller and shallower (Fig. 8H, Stage 5c). We suggest that the decreasing sea-level stimulated the change from Unit III uniform marine sedimentation to the dynamic Unit IV sedimentation and tentatively propose that this happened around 4 cal. ka BP where also Rasmussen *et al.* (2020) suggest a significant change in hydrographic conditions in Aarhus Bay. The hummocky seismic facies with local incisions of Unit IV is particularly well-developed in the shallower water areas near 'the Plate' and it seems reasonable that this area was exposed to wave-driven, longshore sediment transport that may also have contributed to the varied depositional pattern within Unit IV. Towards the centre of the bay, at larger water depths (>6 m), the generally fine-grained sediments of Unit IV (silty clay and gyttja in cores 05G, 12G and R1) concur with a setting in a semi-enclosed embayment where fetch-limited wind waves would have had little effect.

The present-day submarine channel and the associated prograding to aggrading sediments are distinct features of Unit IV. The bottom-current deposits were initiated already during sedimentation of Unit III. We suggest that the bottom current was established during the marine high-stand. The driving process for initiation of the bottom current, however, remains uncertain. Our observations indicate that the bottom current had a significant capacity in removing and redepositing large parts of Unit III (Fig. 5E). The erosion capacity and the relatively large size of the channel contrast with the dimensions of the bay and the water depths (5–20 m). Even during the maximum sea-level high-stand, Kalø Bay was still a small area, with limited water volume and short fetch. Hence, we consider it to be unlikely that the bottom current is wind-driven, although water masses may have been pushed in or out of the bay during storm events (Swatridge *et al.* 2022; van Kouwen *et al.* 2023). The capacity for generating storm-induced currents (surges) is, however, limited due to the small size of the bay (Swatridge *et al.* 2022; van Kouwen *et al.* 2023). Similarly, the tides in the bay would not have differed much from the micro-tidal conditions that prevail in the bay at the present. Together with a low freshwater flux into the bay, this seems to rule-out estuarine circulation as a driver for the bottom current. Wind-generated sea-level gradients between Kalø Bay and Aarhus Bay could be responsible for forming barotropic currents. However, taking the small size of the bay into account, such sea-level gradients would be small, limiting the effect of barotropic flows. In conclusion, the available data do not provide clear evidence for the

driving mechanism of the bottom current system in the bay. The most plausible interpretation is that system was active during storm surges driven by wind set-up (Swatridge *et al.* 2022) and inactive during intermediate conditions. To fully understand the system, the conditions in the larger Aarhus Bay farther south and its inlets during the marine transgression must also be considered.

Over time, the bottom current system migrated north and east, and the channel became narrower (Fig. 6). The reflection pattern of the bottom current deposits furthermore changed from prograding to aggrading (Fig. 5D). This, together with gyttja in the present-day channel, suggest that the channel is currently being infilled and hence no longer active.

Wider implications

The depositional succession in the shallow embayment Kalø Bay record the glacial to postglacial evolution of the area. Due to the generally good preservation of the strata, we can pinpoint distinct stages in the evolution and study the glacial and postglacial features and geological processes in detail. Our results indicate that both the glacial advance succession and the glacial retreat succession are well preserved in the bay. This may indicate a rapid disintegration and recession of the ice lobe from the area, with limited associated erosion. In contrast, the glaciofluvial deglaciation succession appears very condensed in the bay. This is possibly due to both limited deposition (reserved to the deepest parts of the bay) and subsequent reworking during the postglacial transgression. This pattern differs from the extended deglaciation succession in the southern Baltic Sea where thicker successions of lacustrine and marine sediments were deposited in more open water settings throughout the latest Pleistocene and Early Holocene (e.g. Jensen *et al.* 1997, 2005, 2017; Andrén *et al.* 2011). The postglacial succession in the bay is well preserved, with preservation of coastal facies like nearshore bars and extended transgressive and high-stand successions of subunit II_d and Unit III. Compared to other depositional environments like the Baltic Sea lacustrine stages, the shallow embayment appears to have facilitated better preservation of the coastal facies. This is possibly due to the relatively fast transgression occurring across Kalø Bay that to a large degree was governed by the former glacial topography in the bay. For the North Sea region where comparable sea-level rise occurred (e.g. Hijma *et al.* 2025), the former glacial landscape is dominated by Weichselian sandy outwash deposits (e.g. Coughlan *et al.* 2018; Fleischer *et al.* 2022) rather than the morainic morphologies dominating Kalø Bay and the Kattegat region (e.g. Greenwood & Hughes 2022; Vangkilde-Pedersen *et al.* 2025). This sets a very different baseline topography for the postglacial evolution. In the eastern North Sea, the transgressive depositional succession is in addition strongly linked to former, large-scale, fluvial

river valley systems (e.g. Hepp *et al.* 2017; Prins & Andresen 2019; Özmaral *et al.* 2022; Andresen *et al.* 2024), which do not to the same degree occur in Kalø Bay. Such differences in substrate composition and topographic controls form together with the relative sea-level changes, important constraints for the preservation potential of the depositional succession. In the south-western Baltic Sea, the postglacial marine inundation was governed largely by the topographic thresholds in the Danish Belts leading to a more complex depositional succession than what we observe in Kalø Bay, shifting between lacustrine and marine stages (e.g. Bennike & Jensen 1998, 2011; Bennike *et al.* 2004, 2012; Lampe *et al.* 2005, 2011; Rosentau *et al.* 2021). The narrow inlet to Kalø Bay may, however, have posed a similar, but local threshold during the early marine stages.

The depositional succession in Kalø Bay reflects the sea-level changes occurring after the last deglaciation and hence supports that shallow embayments represent sensitive environments. The most significant erosion in the bay is observed for the second flooding surface (Top Unit II) at the transition from transgressive and restricted marine conditions to high-stand, more open marine conditions, and in relation to the present-day submarine channel and reworking of the marine deposits in Unit III and Unit IV. Within the framework of future projected accelerating sea-level rise, information of how erosion varied spatially and temporally can be important for planning mitigation and coastal protection measures.

Besides addressing the preservation potential of the deglaciation and postglacial depositional succession in the bay and assess the effects of sea-level rise, the palaeolandscape reconstruction offers insights into the sediment distribution in the bay. This is important for considerations of geoengineering constraints in relation to constructions at sea and along the coastline, and in general for marine spatial planning and management (cf. Cotterill *et al.* 2017; Kurjanski *et al.* 2021; Prins *et al.* 2025; Vangkilde-Pedersen *et al.* 2025).

The palaeolandscape reconstruction is also important for assessing the geoarchaeological potential of the area (e.g. Andresen *et al.* 2024). Kalø Bay hosts a known Mesolithic submerged settlement (Astrup 2018) and understanding how the landscape evolved in the Early to Mid-Holocene provides additional context to the known archaeology in the bay and aids predictive modelling for additional submerged archaeological sites (e.g. Gregory *et al.* 2021).

Conclusions

In this study, we use subbottom profiles and sediment cores to describe the geological development of Kalø Bay, a shallow embayment located in the south-western Kattegat. Our analysis highlights a complex geological evolution from glacial to shallow marine stages captured by four distinct seismic units that show a variety of pre-

served facies from different depositional settings, including glaciolacustrine, telmatic, limnic and coastal environments. During the Early Holocene, the bay was gradually and possibly stepwise inundated by the Littorina Sea that entered the bay via a narrow inlet in the south. This inlet likely functioned as a threshold controlling the marine influx to the bay according to the subtle balance between eustatic sea-level rise and glacioisostatic rebound. Coastal facies from the inundation in the form of near-shore bars are preserved in the deepest parts of the bay supporting that transgression happened relatively rapid over a few thousand years. With rising sea-level, circulation and oxidation levels in the bay changed. A very distinct feature of the bay is the present-day, submarine channel with its associated prograding to aggrading bottom current deposits. The bottom current system that was likely initiated during the marine sea-level highstand ~6 cal. ka BP, appears to be inactive today, with the channel currently being infilled by gyttja.

The study of Kalø Bay highlights the sensitivity of shallow embayments to sea-level variations. Different processes have influenced the sedimentary record in the bay over time, but with a generally low-tidal regime since the LGM, the main agent in the shallow-water areas of the bay has been wave-driven erosion and deposition. During sea-level highstand, and likely in relation to storm surges, bottom currents with a significant capacity formed in the shallow embayment, reflecting a currently poorly understood mechanism for sedimentation in such environments.

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Data availability statement. – The subbottom profiles are available for download at the marine raw material database Marta managed by GEUS (<https://eng.geus.dk/products-services-facilities/data-and-maps/marine-raw-material-database-marta/>).

References

- Abreu, V., Sullivan, M., Pirmez, C. & Mohrig, D. 2003: Lateral accretion packages (LAPs): an important reservoir element in deep water sinuous channels. *Marine and Petroleum Geology* 20, 631–648. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.marpetgeo.2003.08.003>.
- Andersen, B. 1991: En undersøgelse af holocene foraminiferfauna fra Vilsund i det vestlige Limfjordsområde. *Dansk Geologisk Forening, Arsskrift for 1990–91*, 47–52.
- Andersen, L. T., Anthonsen, K. L. & Jakobsen, P. R. 2024: Danmarks Digitale Jordartskort 1:25.000. Version 7.0. GEUS. *Danmarks og Grønlands Geologiske Undersøgelse Rapport 2023/29*, 30 pp. <https://doi.org/10.22008/gpub/34696>.
- Andrén, T., Björck, S., Andrén, E., Conley, D., Zillén, L. & Anjar, J. 2011: The development of the Baltic Sea basin during the last 130 ka. In Harff, J., Björck, S. & Hoth, P. (eds): *The Baltic Sea Basin*, 75–98. Central and Eastern European Development Studies (CEEDES). Springer, Berlin, Heidelberg. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-642-17220-5_4.
- Andresen, K. J., Dahlin, A., Kjeldsen, K. U., Røy, H., Bennike, O., Nørgaard-Pedersen, N. & Seidenkrantz, M.-S. 2021: The longevity of pockmarks – a case study from a shallow water body in northern Denmark. *Marine Geology* 434, 106440. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.margeo.2021.106440>.
- Andresen, K. J., Hepp, D. A., Keil, H. & Spiess, V. 2024: Seismic morphologies of submerged late glacial to early Holocene landscapes at the eastern Dogger Bank, central North Sea Basin – implications for geo-archaeological potential. *Geological Society of London, Special Publication* 525, 13–42. <https://doi.org/10.1144/SP525-2021-155>.
- Astrup, P. M. 2018: *Sea-Level Change in Mesolithic Southern Scandinavia*. 207 pp. Jutland Archaeological Society, Aarhus.
- Badley, M. E. 1985: *Practical Seismic Interpretation*. 266. International Human Resources Development Corporation, Boston.
- Barboza, E. G., Dillenburg, S. R., Lopes, R. P., Rosa, M. L. C. C., Caron, F., Abreu, V., Manzolli, R. P., Nunes, J. C. R., Weschenfelder, J. & Tomazelli, L. J. 2021: Geomorphological and stratigraphic evolution of a fluvial incision in the coastal plain and inner continental shelf in southern Brazil. *Marine Geology* 437, 106514. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.margeo.2021.106514>.
- Bendixen, C., Boldreel, L. O., Jensen, J. B., Bennike, O., Hübscher, C. & Clausen, O. R. 2017: Early Holocene estuary development of the Hesselø Bay area, southern Kattegat, Denmark and its implication for Ancylus Lake drainage. *Geo-Marine Letters* 37, 579–591. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00367-017-0513-7>.
- Bendixen, C., Jensen, J. B., Bennike, O. & Boldreel, L. O. 2013: Late glacial to early Holocene development of southern Kattegat. *Geological Survey of Denmark and Greenland Bulletin* 28, 21–24. <https://doi.org/10.34194/geusb.v28.4712>.
- Bendixen, C., Jensen, J. B., Boldreel, L. O., Clausen, O. R., Bennike, O., Seidenkrantz, M.-S., Nyberg, J. & Hübscher, C. 2015: The Holocene Great Belt connection to the southern Kattegat, Scandinavia: Ancylus Lake drainage and early Littorina Sea transgression. *Boreas* 46, 53–68. <https://doi.org/10.1111/bor.12154>.
- Bennike, O. & Jensen, J. B. 1998: Late- and postglacial shore level changes in the southwestern Baltic Sea. *Bulletin of the Geological Society of Denmark* 45, 27–38. <https://2dggf.dk/xpdf/bull45-1-27-38.pdf>.
- Bennike, O. & Jensen, J. B. 2011: Postglacial relative shore level changes in Lillebælt, Denmark. *Geological Survey of Denmark and Greenland Bulletin* 23, 37–40. <https://doi.org/10.34194/geusb.v23.4834>.
- Bennike, O., Andreassen, M. S., Jensen, J. B. & Noe-Nyegaard, N. 2012: Early Holocene sea-level changes in Øresund, Scandinavia. *Geolog-*

- ical Survey of Denmark and Greenland Bulletin 26, 29–32. <https://doi.org/10.34194/geusb.v26.4744>.
- Bennike, O., Andresen, K. J., Astrup, P. M., Olsen, J. & Seidenkrantz, M.-S. 2021: Late glacial and Holocene shore-level changes in the Aarhus Bugt area, Denmark. *Geological Survey of Denmark and Greenland Bulletin* 47, 6530. <https://doi.org/10.34194/geusb.v47.6530>.
- Bennike, O., Astrup, P. M., Odgaard, B. V., Pearce, C. & Wiberg-Larsen, P. 2022: Holocene development of Brabrand Fjord, eastern Jylland, Denmark. *Bulletin of the Geological Society of Denmark* 70, 105–115. <https://doi.org/10.37570/bgsd-2022-70-07>.
- Bennike, O., Jensen, J. B., Lemke, W., Kuijpers, A. & Lomholt, S. 2004: Late- and postglacial history of the Great Belt, Denmark. *Boreas* 33, 18–33. <https://doi.org/10.1080/03009480310006952>.
- Blázquez, A. M., López-Belzunce, M., Rodríguez-Pérez, A. E., Guillem, J., Ferrer, C., Nieto, M., Torres, T. & Ortiz, J. E. 2024: The role of the Holocene transgression in the environmental changes of lagoons and marshes of the Mediterranean coast. *Marine Geology* 471, 107286. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.margeo.2024.107286>.
- Boldreel, L. O. & Pedersen, S. A. S. 2024: Neotectonic deformations of the lakebeds in Esrum Sø, eastern Denmark, interpreted to indicate a Postglacial pull-apart basin. *Bulletin of the Geological Society of Denmark* 73, 67–88. <https://doi.org/10.37570/bgsd-2024-73-04>.
- Boyd, R., Dalrymple, R. & Zaitlin, B. A. 1992: Classification of clastic coastal depositional-environments. *Sedimentary Geology* 80, 139–150. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0037-0738\(92\)90037-R](https://doi.org/10.1016/0037-0738(92)90037-R).
- Brennand, T. A. 2000: Deglacial meltwater drainage and glaciodynamics: inferences from Laurentide eskers, Canada. *Geomorphology* 32, 263–293. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0169-555X\(99\)00100-2](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0169-555X(99)00100-2).
- Clausen, O. R., Lykke-Andersen, H., Andresen, K. J. & Normark, E. 2017: Seismisk kortlægning af undergrunden i Mols Bjerge.—Har kalkrygge under Mols Bjerge påvirket isstrømme og dannelsen af israndslandskabet? *Naturrapporter fra Nationalpark Mols Bjerge* 19, 18 pp. <https://nationalparkmolsbjerge.dk/media/z4klo25m/npmb-naturrapport-nr-19-clausen-mfl-seismik-mols-bjerge-2017.pdf>.
- Cotterill, C., Phillips, E., James, L., Forsberg, C.-F. & Tjelta, T. I. 2017: How understanding past landscapes might inform present-day site investigations: a case study from Dogger Bank, southern central North Sea. *Near Surface Geophysics* 15, 403–413. <https://doi.org/10.3997/1873-0604.2017032>.
- Coughlan, M., Fleischer, M., Wheeler, A. J., Hepp, D. A., Hebbeln, D. & Mörz, T. 2018: A revised stratigraphical framework for the Quaternary deposits of the German North Sea sector: a geological–geotechnical approach. *Boreas* 47, 80–105. <https://doi.org/10.1111/bor.12253>.
- Cramer, F. 2018: *Scientific colour maps (8.0.1)*. Software, Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1243862>.
- Dalrymple, R. W. 2023: A review of the morphology, physical processes and deposits of modern straits. *Geological Society of London, Special Publication* 523, 17–83. <https://doi.org/10.1144/SP523-2021-76>.
- Dalrymple, R. W., Zaitlin, B. A. & Boyd, R. 1992: Estuarine facies models; conceptual basis and stratigraphic implications. *Journal of Sedimentary Research* 62, 1130–1146. <https://doi.org/10.1306/D4267A69-2B26-11D7-8648000102C1865D>.
- Davis, R. A. & Clifton, H. E. 1987: Sea-level change and the preservation potential of wave-dominated and tide-dominated coastal sequences. In Nummedal, D., Pilkey, O. H. & Howard, J. D. (eds.): *Sea-Level Fluctuation and Coastal Evolution*, 167–178. SEMP, Tulsa. <https://doi.org/10.2110/pec.87.41.0167>.
- EMODnet 2023: EMODnet Bathymetry OWS services. Available at: <https://ows.emodnet-bathymetry.eu/> (accessed December 2023).
- Evans, D. J. A., Hughes, A. L. C., Hansom, J. D. & Roberts, D. H. 2016: Scottish landform examples 43: Glacifluvial landforms of Strathallan, Perthshire. *Scottish Geographical Journal* 133, 42–53. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14702541.2016.1254276>.
- Faugères, J.-C., Stow, D. A. V., Imbert, P. & Viana, A. 1999: Seismic features diagnostic of contourite drifts. *Marine Geology* 162, 1–38. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0025-3227\(99\)00068-7](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0025-3227(99)00068-7).
- Feldens, P., Diesing, M., Wilken, D. & Schwarzer, K. 2013: Submarine eskers preserved on Adler Grund, south-western Baltic Sea. *Baltica* 26, 137–144. <https://doi.org/10.5200/baltica.2013.26.14>.
- Fischer, A. & Olsen, J. 2021: The Nekselø fish weir and marine reservoir effect in Neolithization period Denmark. *Radiocarbon* 63, 805–820. <https://doi.org/10.1017/RDC.2021.14>.
- Fleischer, M., Abegunrin, A., Hepp, D. A., Kreiter, S., Coughlan, M. & Mörz, T. 2022: Stratigraphic and geotechnical characterization of regionally extensive and highly competent shallow sand units in the southern North Sea. *Boreas* 52, 78–98. <https://doi.org/10.1111/bor.12595>.
- Flury, S., Røy, H., Dale, A. W., Fossing, H., Toth, Z., Spiess, V., Jensen, J. B. & Jørgensen, B. B. 2016: Controls on subsurface methane fluxes and shallow gas formation in Baltic Sea sediment (Aarhus Bay, Denmark). *Geochimica et Cosmochimica Acta* 188, 297–309. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gca.2016.05.037>.
- Fruergaard, M., Johannessen, P. N., Nielsen, L. H., Nielsen, L., Møller, I., Andersen, T. J., Piasecki, S. & Pejrup, M. 2018: Sedimentary architecture and depositional controls of a Holocene wave-dominated barrier-Island system. *Sedimentology* 65, 1170–1212. <https://doi.org/10.1111/sed.12418>.
- Geocenter Denmark 2021: Kystzonens geodynamik i Nationalpark Mols Bjerge. Naturrapporter fra Nationalpark Mols Bjerge 32, 84 pp. Available at: https://nationalparkmolsbjerge.dk/media/opsfbgds/npmb-naturrapport-nr-32-kystzonens_geodynamik_slut-08032021.pdf.
- GEUS 2020: Seabed sediment map of Denmark. Available at: <https://data.geus.dk/geusmap/?lang=da&mapname=denmark#baseMapDa&layers=havbundssediment> (accessed December 2023).
- GEUS 2022: Geomorphological map of Denmark 1:200.000. Available at: https://data.geus.dk/geusmap/?mapname=denmark#layers=dk_kort_morfologi (accessed March 2025).
- GEUS 2023: Height and depth in the Danish area. Available at: http://data.geus.dk/geusmap/?mapname=denmark#layers=hoejde_dybde (accessed August 2023).
- GEUS 2025a: Hillshading of the DHM/Terrain (2007). Available at: https://data.geus.dk/geusmap/?mapname=denmark#layers=sdfe_dhm_2007 (accessed August 2025).
- GEUS 2025b: Geological surface map of Denmark 1:25.000, version 7. Available at: https://data.geus.dk/geusmap/?mapname=denmark#layers=jordartskort_25000 (accessed August 2025).
- Greenwood, S. L. & Hughes, A. L. C. 2022: Chapter 5—Glacial landscapes of Fennoscandia. In Palacios, D., Hughes, P. D., García-Ruiz, J. M. & Andrés, N. (eds.): *European Glacial Landscapes*, 37–43. Elsevier, Amsterdam. <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-12-823498-3.00051-0>.
- Gregory, D. J., Bennike, O., Jensen, J. B., Rasmussen, P. & Al-Hamdani, Z. 2021: Development of predictive Geoarchaeological models to locate and assess the preservation potential of submerged prehistoric sites using remote sensing, Palaeoenvironmental analysis, and GIS. *Heritage* 4, 4678–4699. <https://doi.org/10.3390/heritage4040258>.
- Heaton, T. J., Köhler, P., Butzin, M., Bard, E., Reimer, R. W., Austin, W. E. N., Ramsey, C. B., Grootes, P. M., Hughen, K. A., Kromer, B., Reimer, P. J., Adkins, J., Burke, A., Cook, M. S., Olsen, J. & Skinner, L. C. 2020: Marine20—the marine radiocarbon age calibration curve (0–55,000 cal BP). *Radiocarbon* 62, 779–820. <https://doi.org/10.1017/RDC.2020.68>.
- Hein, C. J., FitzGerald, D. M., Carruthers, E. A., Stone, B. D., Barnhardt, W. A. & Gontz, A. M. 2012: Refining the model of barrier island formation along a paraglacial coast in the Gulf of Maine. *Marine Geology* 307, 40–57. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.margeo.2012.03.001>.
- Hepp, D. A., Warnke, U., Hebbeln, D. & Mörz, T. 2017: Tributaries of the Elbe Palaeovalley: features of a hidden palaeolandscape in the German Bight, North Sea. In Bailey, G. N., Harff, J. & Sakellariou, D. (eds.): *Under the Sea: Archaeology and Palaeolandscapes of the Continental Shelf*, 211–222. *Coastal Research Library* 20. Springer Open, Cham.
- Hijma, M. P., Bradley, S. L., Cohen, K. M., van der Wal, W., Barlow, N. L. M., Frechen, B. B. M., Hennekam, R., van Heteren, S., Kiden, P., Mavritsakis, A., Meijninger, B. M. L., Reichart, G.-J., Reinhardt, L., Rijdsdijk, K. F., Vink, A. & Busschers, F. 2025: Global sea-level rise in the early Holocene revealed from North Sea peats. *Nature* 639, 652–657. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41586-025-08769-7>.

- Hjelstuen, B. O., Sejrup, H. P., Valvik, E. & Becker, L. W. M. 2018: Evidence of an ice-dammed lake outburst in the North Sea during the last deglaciation. *Marine Geology* 402, 118–130. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.margeo.2017.11.021>.
- Houmark-Nielsen, M. 2010: Istidslandskabet omkring Nationalpark Mols Bjerger. *Geologisk Tidsskrift* 2010, 1–25. <https://2dggf.dk/xpdf/gt2010-1-25.pdf>.
- Houmark-Nielsen, M. & Kjær, K. H. 2003: Southwest Scandinavia, 40–15 ka BP: palaeogeography and environmental change. *Journal of Quaternary Science* 18, 769–786. <https://doi.org/10.1002/jqs.802>.
- Hughes, A. L. C., Gyllencreutz, R., Lohne, Ø. S., Mangerud, J. & Svendsen, J. I. 2016: The last Eurasian ice sheets – a chronological database and time-slice reconstruction, DATED-1. *Boreas* 45, 1–45. <https://doi.org/10.1111/bor.12142>.
- Jensen, J. B. & Bennike, O. 2009: Geological setting as background for methane distribution in Holocene mud deposits, Århus Bay, Denmark. *Continental Shelf Research* 29, 775–784. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.csr.2008.08.007>.
- Jensen, J. B., Bennike, O., Lemke, W. & Kuijpers, A. 2005: The Storebælt gateway to the Baltic. *Geological Survey of Denmark and Greenland Bulletin* 7, 45–48. <https://doi.org/10.34194/geusb.v7.4831>.
- Jensen, J. B., Bennike, O., Witkowski, A., Lemke, W. & Kuijpers, A. 1997: The Baltic ice Lake in the southwestern Baltic: sequence-, chrono- and biostratigraphy. *Boreas* 26, 217–236. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1502-3885.1997.tb00853.x>.
- Jensen, J. B., Kuijpers, A., Bennike, O. & Lemke, W. 2002: BALKAT – Østersøen uden grænser. *GEOLOGI – Nyt fra GEUS* 2002, 2–19. <https://www.geus.dk/media/8543/nr-4-2002.pdf>.
- Jensen, J. B., Moros, M., Endler, R. & IODP Expedition 347 Members 2017: The Bornholm Basin, southern Scandinavia: a complex history from Late Cretaceous structural developments to recent sedimentation. *Boreas* 46, 3–17. <https://doi.org/10.1111/bor.12194>.
- Jørgensen, F. 2024: Hvad eksisterende geofysiske grundvandsdata kan fortælle om undergrund og dannelse af Mols Bjerger og omegn. *Naturrapporter fra Nationalpark Mols Bjerger* 44, 34 pp. <https://nationalparkmolsbjerger.dk/media/jz0heodz/npmb-naturrapport-nr-44-2024-joergensen-f-grundvandsdata-fortaeller-om-undergrund-og-dannelse-af-mols-bjerger-mm.pdf>.
- Jørgensen, F. 2025: Har der eksisteret en selvstændig islobe i Kalø Vig? Nye, lokale TEM-undersøgelser og tolkninger af Mols Bjerges glacialt deformerede geologi. *Naturrapporter fra Nationalpark Mols Bjerger* 47, 28 pp. <https://nationalparkmolsbjerger.dk/media/lpthgmv1/npmb-naturrapport-nr-47-2025-joergensen-f-har-der-eksister-et-en-selvstaendig-islobe-i-kaloe-vig.pdf>.
- Jupiter 2023: National Database for boreholes. Available at: <https://data.geus.dk/JupiterWWW/borerapport.jsp?dgunr=561022.1> (accessed December 2023).
- Kirkham, J. D., Hogan, K. A., Larter, R. D., Self, E., Games, K., Huuse, M., Stewart, M. A., Ottesen, D., Le Heron, D. P., Lawrence, A., Kane, I., Arnold, N. S. & Dowdeswell, J. A. 2024: The infill of tunnel valleys in the central North Sea: implications for sedimentary processes, geohazards, and ice-sheet dynamics. *Marine Geology* 467, 107185. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.margeo.2023.107185>.
- van Kouwen, N. C., Ton, A. M., Vos, S. E., Vijverberg, T., Reniers, A. J. H. M. & Aarninkhof, S. G. J. 2023: Quantifying spit growth and its hydrodynamic drivers in wind-dominated lake environments. *Geomorphology* 437, 108799. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.geomorph.2023.108799>.
- Kurjanski, B., Rea, B. R., Spagnolo, M., Cornwell, D. G., Howell, J. & Archer, S. 2020: A conceptual model for glaciogenic reservoirs: from landsystems to reservoir architecture. *Marine and Petroleum Geology* 115, 104205. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.marpetgeo.2019.104205>.
- Kurjanski, B., Rea, B. R., Spagnolo, M., Cornwell, D. G., Howell, J., Comte, J.-C., Gonzalez Quiros, A., Palmu, J.-P., Oien, R. P. & Gibbard, P. L. 2021: Cool deltas: Sedimentological, geomorphological and geophysical characterization of ice-contact deltas and implications for their reservoir properties (Salpausselkä, Finland). *Sedimentology* 68, 3057–3101. <https://doi.org/10.1111/sed.12884>.
- Lambeck, K., Rouby, H., Purcell, Y. S. & Sambridge, M. 2014: Sea-level and global ice volumes from the last glacial maximum to the Holocene. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences of the United States of America* 111, 15296–15303. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.1411762111>.
- Lambeck, K., Smither, C. & Johnston, P. 1998: Sea-level change, glacial rebound and mantle viscosity for northern Europe. *Geophysical Research Letters* 134, 102–144. <https://doi.org/10.1046/j.1365-246X.1998.00541.x>.
- Lampe, R., Endtmann, E., Janke, W., Meyer, H., Lübke, H., Harff, J. & Lemke, W. 2005: A new relative sea-level curve for the Wismar Bay, N-German Baltic coast. (Eine neue relative Meeresspiegelkurve für die Wismarbucht, norddeutsche Ostseeküste). *Meyniana* 57, 5–35.
- Lampe, R., Naumann, M., Meyer, H., Janke, W. & Ziekur, R. 2011: Holocene evolution of the southern Baltic Sea coast and interplay of sea-level variation, isostasy, accommodation and sediment supply. In Harff, J., Björck, S. & Hoth, P. (eds.): *The Baltic Sea Basin*, 233–251. Central and Eastern European Development Studies (CEEDES). Springer, Berlin, Heidelberg. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-642-17220-5_12.
- Larsen, M. M., Jakobsen, H. H., Göke, C., Hendriksen, N. B., Rømer, J. K., Mohn, C., Feld, L., Jensen, A. N. & Schultz, A. C. 2018: Sanitary survey rapport 8: Kalø Vig og Jyllands østkyst (nordligdel). *Teknisk rapport fra DCE – Nationalt Center for Miljø og Energi* 126, 106 pp. Aarhus Universitet, DCE – Nationalt Center for Miljø og Energi. <http://dce2.au.dk/pub/TR126.pdf>.
- Larsen, N. K., Knudsen, K. L., Krohn, C. F., Kronborg, C., Murray, A. S. & Nielsen, O. B. 2009: Late Quaternary ice sheet, lake and sea history of Southwest Scandinavia – a synthesis. *Boreas* 38, 732–761. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1502-3885.2009.00101.x>.
- Larsen, N. K., Kristensen, A. & Buylaert, J.-P. 2017: Datering og dannelse af istids- og mellemistidsaflejringer. *Naturrapporter fra Nationalpark Mols Bjerger* 16, 14 pp. <https://nationalparkmolsbjerger.dk/media/xo3j2xfg/npmb-naturrapport-nr-16-larsen-nk-datering-og-dannelse-af-istidsaflejringer.pdf>.
- Lericolais, G., Popescu, I., Guichard, F., Popescu, S.-M. & Manolakis, L. 2007: Water-level fluctuations in the Black Sea since the Last Glacial Maximum. In Yanko-Hombach, V., Gilbert, A. S., Panin, N. & Dolukhanov, P. M. (eds.): *The Black Sea Flood Question*, 437–452. Springer, Dordrecht.
- Leth, J. O. & Larsen, B. 2014: Kortlægning af Danmarks havbunds-sedimenter før og nu. *Geoviden – geologi og geograf* 2, 2–5. https://www.geoviden.dk/wp-content/uploads/2020/11/Geoviden_2_2014.pdf.
- Leth, J. O. & Novak, B. 2010: Late Quaternary geology of a potential wind-farm area in the Kattegat, southern Scandinavia. *Geological Survey of Denmark and Greenland Bulletin* 20, 31–34. <https://doi.org/10.34194/geusb.v20.4893>.
- Li, S. & Gong, C. 2016: Flow dynamics and sedimentation of lateral accretion packages in sinuous deep-water channels: a 3D seismic case study from the northwestern South China Sea margin. *Journal of Asian Earth Sciences* 124, 233–246. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jseaes.2016.05.008>.
- Lindhorst, S., Betzler, C. & Hass, H. C. 2008: The sedimentary architecture of a Holocene barrier spit (Sylt, German Bight): swash-bar accretion and storm erosion. *Sedimentary Geology* 206, 1–16. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sedgeo.2008.02.008>.
- McGlue, M. M., Dilworth, J. R., Johnson, H. L., Whitehead, S. J., Thigpen, J. R., Yeager, K. M., Woolery, E. W., Brown, S. J., Johnson, S. E., Cearley, C. S., Clark, G. M., Dixon, T. S., Goldsby, R. C., Helfrich, A. L., Hodelka, B. N., Lo, E. L., Domingos-Luz, L., Powell, N. E., Rasbold, G. G. & Swanger, W. R. 2023: Effect of dam emplacement and water level changes on sublacustrine geomorphology and recent sedimentation in Jackson Lake, Grand Teton National Park (Wyoming, United States). *Earth Science, Systems and Society* 3, 10066. <https://doi.org/10.3389/esss.2023.10066>.
- Mertz, E. L. 1924: Oversigt over de sen- og postglaciale Niveauforandringer i Danmark. *Danmarks Geologiske Undersøgelse II* 41, 49. <https://doi.org/10.34194/raekke2.v41.6827>.
- Mitchum, R. M., Vail, P. R. & Sangree, J. B. 1977: Seismic stratigraphy and global changes of sea-level, part 6: stratigraphic interpretation of seismic reflection pattern in depositional sequences. *AAPG Memoir* 26, 117–133.
- Newton, A., Andresen, K. J., Blacker, K. J., Harding, R. & Lebas, E. 2024: Seismic geomorphology: subsurface analyses, data integration and Palaeoenvironment reconstructions – an introduction. *Geologi-*

- cal Society of London, Special Publication 525, 1–11. <https://doi.org/10.1144/SP525-2023-108>.
- Ottesen, D., Dowdeswell, J. A., Benn, D. I., Kristensen, L., Christiansen, H. H., Christensen, O., Hansen, L., Lebesbye, E., Forwick, M. & Vorren, T. O. 2008: Submarine landforms characteristic of glacier surges in two Spitsbergen fjords. *Quaternary Science Reviews* 27, 1583–1599. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.quascirev.2008.05.007>.
- Özmaral, A., Abegunrin, A., Keil, H., Hepp, D. A., Schwenk, T., Lantzsich, H., Mörz, T. & Spiess, V. 2022: The Elbe Palaeovalley: evolution from an ice-marginal valley to a sedimentary trap (SE North Sea). *Quaternary Science Reviews* 282, 107453. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.quascirev.2022.107453>.
- Patruno, S. & Helland-Hansen, W. 2018: Clinoforms and clinoform systems: review and dynamic classification scheme for shorelines, subaqueous deltas, shelf edges and continental margins. *Earth-Science Reviews* 185, 202–233. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.earscirev.2018.05.016>.
- Posamentier, H. W., Paumard, V. & Lang, S. C. 2022: Principles of seismic stratigraphy and seismic geomorphology I: extracting geologic insights from seismic data. *Earth-Science Reviews* 228, 103963. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.earscirev.2022.103963>.
- Prins, L. T. & Andresen, K. J. 2019: Buried late Quaternary channel systems in the Danish North Sea – genesis and geological evolution. *Quaternary Science Reviews* 223, 105943. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.quascirev.2019.105943>.
- Prins, L. T., Andresen, K. J., Owen, M. J. & Knutz, P. C. 2025: A review of subsurface geosystems and de-risking offshore construction in the Danish North Sea. *GEUS Bulletin* 52, 8371. <https://doi.org/10.34194/sj67gw16>.
- Ranasinghe, P. N., Donnelly, J. P., Evans, R. L., Rodysill, J. R., Nanayakkara, N. U., van Hengstum, P. J., Hawkes, A. D., Sullivan, R. M. & Toomey, M. R. 2021: Complex sedimentary processes in large coastal embayments and their potential for coastal morphological and paleo tropical cyclone studies: a case study from Choctawhatchee Bay Western Florida, U.S.A. *Marine Geology* 437, 106478. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.margeo.2021.106478>.
- Rasmussen, P., Pantopoulos, G., Jensen, J. B., Olsen, J., Røy, H. & Bennike, O. 2020: Holocene sedimentary and environmental development of Aarhus Bay, Denmark – a multi-proxy study. *Boreas* 49, 108–128. <https://doi.org/10.1111/bor.12408>.
- Reading, H. G. 1996: *Sedimentary Environments: Processes, Facies and Stratigraphy*, vol. 704. Blackwell Publishing, Oxford.
- Rebesco, M., Hernández-Molina, F. J., Van Rooij, D. & Wählin, A. 2014: Contourites and associated sediments controlled by deep-water circulation processes: state-of-the-art and future considerations. *Marine Geology* 352, 111–154. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.margeo.2014.03.011>.
- Reimer, P. and 41 others 2020: The IntCal20 Northern Hemisphere radiocarbon age calibration curve (0–55 cal kB). *Radiocarbon* 62, 725–757. <https://doi.org/10.1017/RDC.2020.41>.
- Reynaud, J. Y. & Dalrymple, R. W. 2012: Shallow-marine tidal deposits. In Davis, J. R. & Dalrymple, R. (eds.): *Principles of Tidal Sedimentology*, 335–369. Springer, Dordrecht. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-94-007-0123-6_13.
- Riis, M. H., Sander, L., Nielsen, L., Buylaert, J.-P., Challier, A. J. M. & Larsen, N. K. 2024: Middle and Late Holocene relative sea level changes and coastal development at Rugård, Denmark. *Boreas* 53, 56–70. <https://doi.org/10.1111/bor.12642>.
- Rosentau, A., Klemann, V., Bennike, O., Steffen, H., Wehr, J., Latinović, M., Bagge, M., Ojala, A., Berglund, M., Becher, G. P., Schoning, K., Hansson, A., Nielsen, L., Clemmensen, L. B., Hede, M. U., Kroon, A., Pejrup, M., Sander, L., Statteger, K., Schwarzer, K., Lampe, R., Lampe, M., Uścińowicz, S., Bitinas, A., Grudzinska, I., Vassiljev, J., Nirgi, T., Kublitskiy, Y. & Subetto, D. 2021: A Holocene relative sea-level database for the Baltic Sea. *Quaternary Science Reviews* 266, 107071. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.quascirev.2021.107071>.
- Röthlisberger, H. 1972: Water pressure in intra- and subglacial channels. *Journal of Glaciology* 11, 177–203. <https://doi.org/10.3189/S0022143000022188>.
- Sander, L., Fruergaard, M., Koch, J., Johannessen, P. N. & Pejrup, M. 2015: Sedimentary indications and absolute chronology of Holocene relative sea-level changes retrieved from coastal lagoon deposits on Samsø, Denmark. *Boreas* 44, 706–720. <https://doi.org/10.1111/bor.12124>.
- Sander, L., Hede, M. U., Fruergaard, M., Nielsen, L., Clemmensen, L. B., Kroon, A., Johannessen, P. N., Nielsen, L. H. & Pejrup, M. 2016: Coastal lagoons and beach ridges as complementary sedimentary archives for the reconstruction of Holocene relative sea-level changes. *Terra Nova* 28, 43–49. <https://doi.org/10.1111/ter.12187>.
- Sandersen, P. & Jørgensen, F. 2016: Kortlægning af begravede dale i Danmark. Opdatering 2015. 107 pp. GEUS Særdugivelse. Available at: https://www.begravededale.dk/PDF_2015/091116_Rapport_Begravede_dale_BIND_1_Endelig_udgave_Low_res.pdf.
- Smed, P. 1981: *Landskabskort over Danmark, Blad 2 Midtjylland*. Geografforlaget, København.
- Soe, N. E., Kroon, A., Odgaard, B. V., Lykke-Andersen, H. & Kristiansen, S. M. 2018: Bathymetric control of Holocene spit migration in a lacustrine environment. *The Holocene* 28, 1245–1254. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0959683618771498>.
- Stokes, C. R. 2017: Geomorphology under ice streams: moving from form to process. *Earth Surface Processes and Landforms* 43, 85–123. <https://doi.org/10.1002/esp.4259>.
- Stokes, C. R., Spagnolo, M. & Clark, C. D. 2011: The composition and internal structure of drumlins: complexity, commonality, and implications for a unifying theory of their formation. *Earth-Science Reviews* 107, 398–422. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.earscirev.2011.05.001>.
- Storrar, R. D., Evans, D. J. A., Stokes, C. R. & Ewertowski, M. 2015: Controls on the location, morphology and evolution of complex esker systems at decadal timescales, Breiðamerkurjökull, southeast Iceland. *Earth Surface Processes and Landforms* 40, 1421–1438. <https://doi.org/10.1002/esp.3725>.
- Stuiver, M. & Polach, H. 1977: Discussion: reporting of ¹⁴C data. *Radiocarbon* 19, 355–363. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0033822200003672>.
- Swatridge, L. L., Mulligan, R. P., Boegman, L., Shan, S. & Valipour, R. 2022: Coupled modelling of storm surge, circulation and surface waves in a large stratified lake. *Journal of Great Lakes Research* 48, 1520–1535. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jglr.2022.08.023>.
- Thomas, G. S. P. & Montague, E. 1997: The morphology, stratigraphy and sedimentology of the Carstairs esker, Scotland, U.K. *Quaternary Science Reviews* 16, 661–674. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0277-3791\(97\)00014-0](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0277-3791(97)00014-0).
- Vangkilde-Pedersen, T. G., Christensen, N., Nørgaard-Pedersen, N., Allaart, L., Bennike, O., Leth, J. O., Winther, L. H., Sandersen, P., Prins, L. T., Singhroha, S. & Pérez, L. F. 2025: Bedre geologiske data til udbygning af havvind – Overordnet geologisk kortlægning af det danske havområde for Energistyrelsen. *GEUS Danmarks og Grønlands Geologiske Undersøgelse Rapport Bind 2025* 29, 297 pp. <https://doi.org/10.22008/gpub/34786>.
- Vardy, M. E., Pinson, L. J. W., Bull, J. M., Dix, J. K., Henstock, T. J., Davis, J. W. & Gutowski, M. 2010: 3D seismic imaging of buried Younger Dryas mass movement flows: Lake Windermere, UK. *Geomorphology* 118, 176–187. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.geomorph.2009.12.017>.
- Vestøl, O., Ågren, J., Steffen, H., Kierulf, H. & Tarasov, L. 2019: NKG2016LU: a new land uplift model for Fennoscandia and the Baltic Region. *Journal of Geodesy* 93, 1759–1779. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00190-019-01280-8>.
- Vink, A., Steffen, H., Reinhardt, L. & Kaufmann, G. 2007: Holocene relative sea-level change, isostatic subsidence and the radial viscosity structure of the mantle of northwest Europe (Belgium, The Netherlands, Germany, southern North Sea). *Quaternary Science Reviews* 26, 3249–3275. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.quascirev.2007.07.014>.